

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-52-IG-30% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221029
Vial:	60	Acq. Method Set:	30%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 52
Injection Volume:	1.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/29/2022 19:29:30 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:52:53 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.061	2090475	49.63	182290
2	8.552	2121751	50.37	142865

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-58-IG-30% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	114	Acq. Method Set:	30%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	lm 4 58
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/4/2022 16:55:58 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:52:36 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.939	3303333	94.99	278989
2	8.041	174348	5.01	12366